
Enhancing Learning Management Systems with AI: Recommendations from Moodle Usage

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Abstract

Learning Management Systems (LMS) are defined as web-based platforms designed to facilitate the planning, delivery, management, and assessment of educational courses and training programs. These systems provide a structured virtual environment where learners, instructors, and administrators can interact through various tools. With the advent of artificial intelligence, several approaches have been explored to reshape and adapt LMS functionalities, enhancing their ability to meet the growing demand for AI-based tools in various pedagogical activities. Among existing LMS platforms, Moodle is one of the most widely used. It facilitates online education and offers a rich array of tools. However, feedback from computer science students highlights both its strengths and areas for improvement, particularly in terms of usability, engagement, and automation. This paper analyzes student feedback and examines how artificial intelligence (AI) can address common challenges in Moodle. Furthermore, it discusses potential AI-driven enhancements based on student insights and proposes recommendations for future research and implementation.

Keywords: Learning Management systems, Moodle, Student's perception, Artificial Intelligence.

1 Introduction

The rapid advancement of information and communication technologies (ICTs) has significantly transformed various aspects of daily life, including education. Over the past decades, learning environments have evolved in response to major technological shifts, such as the rise of the internet, the introduction of Web 2.0 applications, and more recently, the emergence of artificial intelligence (AI)-driven tools [13, 31]. These developments have reshaped how educational content is delivered, accessed, and personalized.

In particular, Learning Management Systems (LMS) have become essential in modern education, enabling institutions to manage courses, facilitate communication, and support online learning. LMS platforms accommodate various teaching and learning methodologies, offering tools for content delivery, assessments, collaboration, and administrative management. However, as technology continues to advance, LMS platforms must adapt to evolving educational needs and user expectations.

The COVID-19 pandemic accelerated the global reliance on LMS platforms, highlighting both their strengths and limitations. Institutions worldwide were compelled to transition rapidly to online learning, revealing challenges related to usability, student engagement, automation, and scalability [22]. Among the widely adopted LMS platforms, Moodle stands out due to its open-source nature, flexibility, and extensive adoption by universities and institutions worldwide, including in Algeria. Its features, such as collaborative tools, integration with external applications, and customizable learning environments, contribute to its success [11]. However, feedback from computer science students suggests areas for improvement, particularly in terms of usability, functionality, and interactivity.

This paper explores the evolution of LMS platforms and examines how AI-driven enhancements could address current limitations in Moodle. By leveraging intelligent tutoring systems, automated grading, AI-powered chatbots, and adaptive learning algorithms, AI has the potential to enhance personalized learning, improve engagement, and optimize administrative tasks. The insights presented in this paper are based on reflections and feedback from Master's level computer science students, who offer valuable perspectives on potential improvements at various levels, including functionality, usability, and advanced AI-driven features.

This paper aims to:

- Provide an overview of LMS evolution and highlight challenges in Moodle.
- Analyze student feedback to identify key areas for improvement.

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- Propose AI-driven enhancements that could improve interactivity, automation, and personalization.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents an overview on LMS and AI integration. Section 3 presents the methodology used for gathering student insights. Section 4 outlines key findings and proposed AI-based recommendations. Finally, Section 5 concludes the paper.

2 Background

2.1 LMS Overview

A Learning Management systems (LMS) is defined as virtual environment that aims to simulate face-to-face learning environments with the use of Information Technology applications, and customizable learning environments, contribute to its success [27]. The interactions among different users (student, teacher, administrative) happen through the system that provides synchronous or asynchronous communication tools. LMS provide a large plethora of functions allowing the creation of different strategies and learning modes and to engage learners.

Figure 1: LMS functions

Learning Management System (LMS) are designed to include several components that support online education course administration, and student engagement [29, 19]. The main functions of an LMS are depicted in Figure 1. Course registration and administration module manages user roles, course enrollment, group organization, scheduling, and authentication. Content delivery enables both synchronous and asynchronous learning, supporting various formats such as videos, interactive materials, and allow students to engage flexibly with course content by offering possibility to connect with different devices. To monitor progress, LMS platforms integrate tracking and learning analytics, providing insights into student engagement, course completion rates, and attendance. Another essential component is collaboration and communication, which fosters interaction through chat systems, discussion forums, shared calendars, and resource-sharing tools, while also offering advanced collaboration features such as wikis and co-creation workspaces. Effective course material management ensures that educational resources are organized, and accessible, integrating with different types of repositories. Finally, the assessment and evaluation module facilitates automated quizzes, peer reviews, Exams, and competency-based assessments, allowing instructors to efficiently measure learning outcomes. Together, these components create a comprehensive digital learning environment, enabling institutions to deliver engaging, interactive, and structured online education.

2.2 Artificial Intelligence in LMS

With the advent of artificial intelligence applications, learning management systems through their components have evolved to adapt to the new requirements. Several efforts have been made to improve the

LMS function with artificial intelligence applications and tools [9, 7, 1].

This section aims to present the current utilization of AI in Learning Management Systems by exploring the interaction of AI with every aspect of LMS and providing references supporting the integration and elucidating the benefits and challenges of such endeavor. Table 1 illustrates AI enhancements for every LMS components with supporting references.

Table 1: AI Enhancements for LMS Components

LMS Component	AI Enhancements
Registration and Administration	AI-based automated student registration [18], intelligent course recommendations [25, 21], and adaptive scheduling [5, 15].
Content Delivery	Personalized learning paths [33, 16], adaptive content recommendations [8, 30], and real-time AI tutoring [12, 34].
Tracking and Analytics	Predictive analytics for student performance [20, 6], engagement tracking [14].
Collaboration	Chatbots for student assistance, automated discussion moderation, and intelligent group formation [26, 24].
Course Material Management	Assisted content organization, tagging and summarization, and intelligent resource recommendations [35, 23, 4].
Assessment and Evaluation	Automated essay scoring and plagiarism detection, [2, 10].

The table 1 illustrates the availability of research on the integration of AI tools and applications to enhance learning management systems (LMS) at different levels. It is worth noting that the integration of artificial intelligence in LMS has shifted significantly with the advent of generative AI. Indeed, tools like ChatGPT have revolutionized LMS functionalities with their unique capabilities in natural language understanding and content generation [28]. These advancements have enabled more interactive and adaptive learning experiences facilitating AI-based tutoring and assistance, assessment, and personalization.

Among existing platforms, Moodle is a fundamental tool in modern education, particularly in computer science programs. It facilitates course management, content delivery, and student-teacher interaction. AI applications have been integrated into various aspects of LMS platforms through several initiatives [17]. However, student feedback continues to highlight usability concerns, a lack of real-time support, and difficulties in navigating and engaging with course materials. This indicates that the integration of AI tools remains an active research area. The aim of this study is to analyze feedback from computer science students on Moodle and explore how AI technologies can enhance its functionality.

3 Methodology

This section outlines the research methodology used in this study. It begins by describing the research model, followed by details on the context, participants, and data collection.

3.1 Research Model

This study is based on a qualitative research approach. Qualitative research focuses on understanding meanings, experiences, and concepts from the perspective of participants. Its objective is to gain insights into social phenomena, events, or complex issues. This type of research was adopted because it is best suited to capture the different aspects of users' reactions to the use of Moodle platform enabling the evaluation of its strengths, weaknesses, and potential improvements [3].

To gather data, the study employs a questionnaire, which is one of the most commonly used tools in educational technology research. The questionnaire consists of open-ended questions, allowing assessment and qualitative insights. The collected responses are analyzed to identify trends, user satisfaction, and key areas where AI-driven enhancements could improve the platform.

3.2 Context and Participants

The study was conducted with final-year Master's students from the Computer Science Department of Boumerdes University. A total of 54 students participated in the survey. As young engineers and future professionals, their insights are particularly valuable in identifying technical and functional improvements for the Moodle platform. The questionnaire covered three main areas:

- Advantages of Moodle: Students were asked to identify key benefits of using the platform.
- Challenges and Limitations: Participants highlighted areas they think about as Moodle limitations.
- Suggestions for Improvement: As computer science students, participants provided some directions to enhance the platform.

The collected data was analyzed qualitatively to identify recurring patterns and common themes. Additionally, percentage distributions were used to highlight the frequency of reported advantages and challenges. The results provide insights and a base for recommendations for improving Moodle's usability and performance.

4 Results

This section presents students' feedback related to the questions about advantages, inconveniences, and possible improvements for Moodle. The last point serves as a basis to propose recommendations for improvements by including AI tools and applications.

4.1 Strengths of the platform

The number of students responding to the question about Moodle advantages is twenty six (26 students). The following key points emerged about the platform strengths: flexibility and accessibility, collaboration, pedagogical support, security and data protection, and digital skills development. The data are reported on Table 2.

The majority of students (88%) pointed out the advantage of the platform flexibility and accessibility. The platform is open-source platform, free and highly customizable. Moodle supports distance learning by eliminating spatial and temporal constraints. The platform benefits also from an active global community that provides extensive documentation and support. The platform is widely adopted by universities, high schools, and businesses. The student also highlighted the advantage of collaboration. Indeed, the platform enables extensive communication between students and teachers. with a rich range of features from simple messaging and forums to more advanced features such as wikis. Coordination is facilitated by planning tools such as shared agendas. Co-production, information sharing, and knowledge management are also features that enhance collaborative work within the learning process, fostering an interactive and engaging educational environment.

Pedagogical Support is mentioned as an advantage of Moodle. Diverse resource formats and evaluation methods are available, enabling teachers to monitor student progress, provide feedback, track behaviors, and digitally assess assignments. The platform is widely used across various educational and organizational contexts, fostering a large community of users and shared resources. Its features help address challenges such as student absences by maintaining course records before, during, and after sessions. With a wide range of integrated tools, online assessment methods, and compatibility with institutional learning environments, Moodle enhances both teaching effectiveness and student engagement. Several students mentioned also security and data protection. The platform offers various mechanisms to protect user data and ensure safe usage. It includes access control features to prevent unauthorized access making Moodle a reliable choice for institutions that prioritize data protection in online learning environments.

Finally, some students (15%) mentioned digital Skills development as an advantage of Moodle since from their point of view Moodle contributes to the development of students' digital skills by providing an environment that encourages the use of technology in learning. The interaction with the platform allow students to enhance their ability to navigate digital tools, manage online resources, and engage in technology-assisted learning.

Table 2: Advantages of Moodle as reported by students

Advantage	% of Students mentioning it
Flexibility and accessibility	88%
Collaboration	50%
Pedagogical support	65%
Security and data protection	38%
Digital skills development	15%

4.2 Weaknesses of the platform

The number of students who responded to the question of the platform weaknesses is 28. It is a different group from the students who responded to the question of advantages. According to students feedback, the platform suffers from several drawbacks that are categorized into four categories as depicted by Table 3: Interface and Usability Issues, lack of personalization, socialization issues, and integration and compatibility problems.

The issues with the interface and use were the most mentioned weakness. Students frequently expressed dissatisfaction with Moodle’s interface, describing it as unattractive, un-intuitive, and outdated. Many reported difficulties navigating the platform. There is a strong demand for a more modern and ergonomic design. Additionally, slow system performance and long loading times make access to learning materials difficult. Several students expressed the need for technical support and training to help users better navigate and utilize the platform’s features effectively. The second raised issue is related to personalization: Students highlighted Moodle’s limited customization options as a drawback. The platform does not sufficiently adapt to students’ specific needs, making it difficult to adapt the learning experience. Many users expressed a request for personalization, both in terms of content and page appearance, to create a more engaging and individualized environment.

Students also raised the need for socialization: they highlighted the lack of features that enhance social interaction, particularly the need for better support for group work. They also pointed out the absence of more engaging activities inspired by social networks, such as the ability for students to publish content and collaborate on co-produced materials. Problems related to integration and compatibility are also reported by students. Students reported difficulties in integrating Moodle with external tools such as Google Drive, Slack, and Zoom, which are highly used in their learning activities. Issues with mobile compatibility are also mentioned , noting that the platform does not always function easily on smartphones and the lack of proper synchronization across devices makes it difficult to use.

Table 3: Weaknesses of Moodle as reported by students

Weakness	% of students mentioning it
Interface and usability issues	88%
Lack of personalization	46%
Socialization issues	23%
Integration and compatibility problems	23%

4.3 Suggestions for Moodle improvements

The objective of this section is first to present students’ suggestions according to the raised issues. These suggestions with the weaknesses that are pointed out by students serve a a basis to some recommendations about the use of AI to enhance the platform.

4.3.1 Sugesions from students

The word cloud (see Figure 2) visually represents the most frequently mentioned suggestions from students regarding Moodle’s improvement. The larger words indicate the most common themes, highlighting key areas of concern and potential enhancements. From this visualization, it is evident that students prioritize aspects such as interface modernization, personalization, integration with other tools, and per-

5 Conclusion

Learning Management Systems (LMS) have revolutionized digital education by providing a structured and interactive environment for learning. This study explored LMS platforms, particularly Moodle through students' perception. The platform offers numerous advantages such as accessibility, collaboration, pedagogical support, security, and flexibility. However, student feedback reveals critical areas for improvement, particularly user interface design, personalization, social interaction, and integration with external tools.

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into LMS platforms presents an opportunity to address these challenges and enhance the overall learning experience. AI applications and features such as adaptive learning, intelligent tutoring systems, automated content recommendations, and predictive analytics can significantly improve the students' experience in LMS. Furthermore, the emergence of Large Language Model (LLM) chatbots like ChatGPT can reshape student interactions within learning environments. This paper provides some recommendations for the use of AI in Moodle. Future directions of this research will address some limitations such as the inclusion of teachers perception, complete with a quantitative research, and the effective development of improvements based on AI.

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